

Review Paper

Experimental Investigation of Polypropylene Fiber-Reinforced Concrete Mechanical Properties and Durability

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ABSTRACT

This study presents an experimental investigation on the mechanical behaviour and durability characteristics of two types of concrete: conventional concrete and polypropylene fiber reinforced concrete (PFRC). The primary objective is to examine the influence of incorporating polypropylene fibers into the concrete matrix and to evaluate how fiber addition affects compressive strength and overall performance. The experimental program focuses on comparing the strength characteristics of normal concrete with PFRC mixtures containing different fiber proportions. The findings aim to identify an optimal fiber dosage that improves crack resistance and enhances the durability of concrete structures.

INTRODUCTION

Concrete is one of the most widely used construction materials due to its high compressive strength and durability. However, it possesses relatively low tensile strength and is susceptible to cracking, shrinkage, and brittle failure. These limitations can affect the structural integrity and long-term service life of concrete structures. One of the effective approaches to improve the performance of concrete is the incorporation of fibers. Polypropylene fibers are commonly used in

concrete to enhance its resistance to cracking, improve ductility, and increase durability. In addition, these fibers help control plastic shrinkage cracks and improve the post-cracking behaviour of concrete. Another important advantage of polypropylene fibers is their ability to reduce the risk of spalling when concrete structures are exposed to high temperatures or fire. High-strength concrete is particularly vulnerable to explosive spalling during fire exposure. The inclusion of polypropylene fibers helps create small channels in the concrete matrix during

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heating, allowing vapor pressure to escape and reducing the chances of surface damage. Furthermore, fiber-reinforced concrete requires less skilled labor during placement and finishing compared to conventional reinforcement methods. This contributes to reduced construction time and overall project cost. Although the addition of polypropylene fibers does not significantly change the compressive strength or modulus of elasticity, it considerably improves tensile strength, flexural strength, and crack resistance.

Problem Statement

1. Conventional concrete exhibits low tensile strength and tends to develop cracks due to shrinkage and external loads, which can reduce the durability and performance of structures.
2. Enhancing the mechanical properties and long-term durability of concrete remains a major challenge in the construction industry, especially under varying environmental conditions such as temperature changes, moisture, and loading.
3. Although polypropylene fibres are known to improve crack resistance and toughness, further experimental studies are required to evaluate their effectiveness in improving the mechanical performance of concrete.

Objectives of the Study

1. To investigate the compressive strength of concrete containing different proportions of polypropylene fibres.
2. To determine the optimum fibre dosage that provides improved mechanical performance while maintaining workable concrete.

Methodology Adopted for Study

The following methodology is adopted to conduct the experimental investigation:

- Collection of relevant research information from national and international journals, textbooks, technical magazines, and online resources.
- Selection of suitable materials required for concrete production such as cement, foundry sand, aggregates, water, and polypropylene fibers.
- Preparation of concrete mixes with varying fiber content.
- Casting and curing of concrete specimens according to standard procedures.
- Testing of specimens to evaluate mechanical properties such as compressive strength.
- Comparison and analysis of results obtained from conventional concrete and PFRC mixtures.

Future Scope of the Study

1. Optimization of Fiber Content

Future studies can focus on identifying the most effective fibre percentage and fibre length that provide the best combination of strength, durability, and workability.

2. Application in Different Concrete Grades

Further research may extend this investigation to different concrete grades such as M20, M30, and M40 to understand the performance of polypropylene fibres in various structural applications.

3. Durability under Severe Environmental Conditions

Additional studies can evaluate the behaviour of PFRC when exposed to harsh conditions such as freeze–thaw cycles, chemical attack, and elevated temperatures.

4. Sustainable Construction Applications

Future research can also explore combining polypropylene fibres with recycled aggregates or supplementary cementitious materials such as fly ash, silica fume, and ground granulated blast furnace slag to develop more environmentally sustainable concrete.

CONCLUSION

The experimental comparison between conventional concrete and polypropylene fibre reinforced concrete indicates that the addition of polypropylene fibers improves the overall performance of concrete. While plain concrete tends to behave as a brittle material, the inclusion of fibres enhances ductility and crack resistance. Polypropylene fibres are effective in controlling shrinkage cracks, increasing impact resistance, and improving durability. Although the compressive strength of concrete does not significantly change, the improvement in tensile and flexural behaviour makes PFRC a suitable material for modern construction applications. Therefore, the use of polypropylene fibres can contribute to stronger, more durable, and more reliable concrete structures.

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